

BALANCING THE LOAD: A QUALITATIVE ACTION RESEARCH ON TEACHER WORKLOAD AND INSTRUCTIONAL QUALITY

Milcaren C. Burtanog, Vel Jayco P. Palmes

Negros Oriental State University, Dumaguete City, Negros Oriental, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

This qualitative action research examined the workload experiences of eight graduate student-teachers at Negros Oriental State University in Dumaguete City and its impact on instructional quality. Guided by the Job Demands–Resources (JD-R) Model, the study explored how teacher-learners balanced professional teaching responsibilities, graduate studies, and personal obligations, as well as the challenges, coping strategies, and institutional support associated with workload management. Data were collected using a structured survey questionnaire with both closed-ended and open-ended items and analyzed through thematic analysis, supported by member checking to ensure credibility. Findings revealed that participants experienced heavy workloads due to multiple responsibilities, including lesson preparation, assessment, administrative tasks, graduate school requirements, and personal obligations, often resulting in extended working hours and occasional stress. Time constraints, excessive documentation, high expectations, and limited resources emerged as primary challenges, while participants employed strategies such as task organization, prioritization, collaboration, use of technology, and self-care to maintain instructional effectiveness and well-being. The study also highlighted that strong institutional support, including reduction of administrative tasks, provision of teaching resources, mentorship, and collaborative school environments, was perceived as essential for sustaining instructional quality and teacher well-being. These findings emphasize the complex interplay between workload, professional resilience, and systemic support, providing practical insights for schools and higher education institutions to enhance teacher performance, work-life balance, and instructional outcomes.

Keywords: *teacher workload, graduate student-teachers, instructional quality, workload management*

INTRODUCTION

Teachers play a vital role in ensuring quality instruction and meaningful learning experiences for students. However, in recent years, teachers have increasingly been burdened with responsibilities beyond classroom teaching. These responsibilities included lesson planning, assessment, administrative paperwork, documentation requirements, research activities, participation in school programs, and compliance with various institutional requirements. As educational systems evolve, teachers are expected to perform multiple roles that extend beyond instruction, which significantly increases their workload. Studies have emphasized that excessive workload contributed to teacher stress, emotional exhaustion, and reduced job satisfaction, which negatively affected teaching performance and instructional focus (Schulze-Hagenest et al., 2023).

In the Philippine educational context, teacher workload has been recognized as a persistent issue affecting teaching effectiveness and professional well-being. Teachers were expected not only to deliver quality instruction but also to comply with numerous administrative duties and institutional obligations. International reports highlighted that increasing administrative and non-teaching responsibilities significantly reduced teachers' ability to focus on instructional activities (OECD et al., 2022; OECD, 2023). Consequently, teachers often experienced workload intensification, which limited the time available for instructional preparation, reflective practice, and effective classroom engagement.

Instructional quality refers to the effectiveness of teaching practices that promote meaningful learning and student engagement. Maintaining high instructional quality requires adequate time for lesson preparation, the use of appropriate teaching strategies, learner engagement, assessment of student performance, and reflection on teaching practices. However, research suggested that when teachers experienced heavy workload and time constraints, their ability to maintain high instructional quality was often compromised (Gudelos & Mabitad, 2025). Moreover, teacher well-being played a crucial role in sustaining instructional quality, as teachers experiencing stress and fatigue due to excessive workload showed decreased motivation and instructional efficiency (Collie, 2021).

The challenges associated with teacher workload became even more complex for educators who were simultaneously pursuing graduate studies. Teachers enrolled in graduate programs often faced the dual role of being both educators and learners, balancing classroom teaching with academic coursework, research requirements, and personal responsibilities. Scholars emphasized that these dual roles intensified workload pressure and made it difficult for teacher-learners to allocate sufficient time and energy for instructional improvement (Kim & Asbury, 2020). At Negros Oriental State University in Dumaguete City, many graduate students in teacher education programs were full-time

teachers who had to manage professional responsibilities alongside academic commitments, which influenced their instructional practices and performance.

Several studies explored the relationship between teacher workload and instructional quality. Research indicated that workload intensification negatively affected lesson preparation, classroom engagement, and overall teaching effectiveness (Pacaol, 2021; Gudelos & Mabitad, 2025). High workload was also associated with emotional exhaustion and reduced job satisfaction among teachers (Schulze-Hagenest et al., 2023). However, studies suggested that institutional support, collaborative practices, and effective leadership could help mitigate workload pressures and support teachers in maintaining quality instruction (Almodiel, 2025; Kim & Asbury, 2020; Cachero et al., 2026). Workplace support, including leadership from school administrators and peer collaboration, was likewise found to influence teachers' ability to manage workload and sustain teaching effectiveness (Collie, 2021).

This study was anchored on the Job Demands–Resources (JD-R) Model proposed by Bakker and Demerouti (2017), which explains how job demands and job resources influence employee well-being and performance. In this framework, teacher workload represented the job demands that may have influenced instructional quality, while job resources such as institutional support, collaboration, professional development, and time management strategies helped mitigate the negative effects of these demands (Gudelos & Mabitad, 2025; Kim & Asbury, 2020). Guided by this perspective, the present qualitative action research examined how selected graduate student-teachers of Negros Oriental State University in Dumaguete City balanced their workload and how this balance influenced their instructional quality, with the aim of identifying strategies that may help improve both teacher well-being and instructional effectiveness.

Research Questions

This study examined the workload experiences of selected graduate student-teachers at Negros Oriental State University, Dumaguete City. It focused on understanding how teachers managed their teaching responsibilities while fulfilling other professional demands and maintaining instructional quality. The study explored the challenges teachers encountered, the effects of workload on their well-being and instructional focus, the strategies they used to manage their responsibilities, and the types of support they needed from their schools. To guide the investigation, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. How do selected graduate student-teachers describe their current workload and daily teaching responsibilities?
2. What challenges do graduate student-teachers encounter in balancing teaching duties and other non-teaching responsibilities?
3. How does teacher workload affect their instructional focus, well-being, and job satisfaction?
4. What strategies do graduate student-teachers use to manage their workload and maintain their well-being?

5. What forms of school support do graduate student-teachers perceive as necessary to balance workload and maintain instructional quality?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized a qualitative action research design to explore the workload experiences of selected graduate student-teachers at Negros Oriental State University, Dumaguete City, and its impact on instructional quality. Action research was deemed appropriate because it focused on identifying real challenges within the participants' professional context and sought practical strategies to improve teaching practices and workload management. Through this approach, the study aimed not only to understand the experiences of graduate student-teachers but also to generate insights and actionable recommendations to enhance their instructional effectiveness and well-being.

Data were collected using a survey questionnaire containing both closed-ended and open-ended items. The closed-ended questions employed checklists to capture patterns in workload perception, challenges, strategies, and school support, while the open-ended questions allowed participants to provide detailed reflections on their daily routines, obstacles, coping mechanisms, and suggestions for improvement. This combination of structured and descriptive data enabled the researchers to obtain a comprehensive understanding of how teachers managed their workload, the effects on instructional quality, and the types of support needed to maintain a healthy work-life balance.

The data collected were analyzed using thematic analysis, a qualitative method that identifies, organizes, and interprets patterns or themes within the data. First, the researchers performed data familiarization by carefully reading and reviewing all responses multiple times to gain a thorough understanding of participants' experiences. Next, data interpretation was conducted by analyzing the themes to answer the research questions, exploring connections between themes to identify patterns, underlying causes, and potential solutions. To ensure validation of findings, preliminary results were shared with participants through member checking to confirm that their experiences and perspectives were accurately represented. Finally, the findings were presented descriptively, supported by direct quotes from participants to ensure authenticity and clarity of interpretation. This systematic approach ensured that the analysis was transparent, reliable, and reflective of the participants' real experiences, providing meaningful insights for improving teacher workload management and instructional quality.

Research Locale

The study was conducted at Negros Oriental State University (NORSU) in Dumaguete City, a higher education institution offering graduate programs in education for practicing teachers. The research focused on graduate student-teachers who were actively

engaged in teaching while pursuing their graduate studies, making NORSU an ideal setting to examine the dual demands of professional and academic responsibilities. This locale provided a dynamic environment to explore how teachers managed workload, implemented coping strategies, and sought school support, with the aim of understanding the impact of these factors on instructional quality and teacher well-being.

Research Participants

The participants of this study consisted of public school teachers who were concurrently enrolled as graduate students at Negros Oriental State University in Dumaguete City, selected from various public schools across Negros Oriental where they were employed. These individuals were purposively chosen due to their direct experience in managing the dual responsibilities of teaching and graduate studies, rendering them particularly suited to provide informed insights on workload management and instructional quality. The study involved a total of eight participants, each with a minimum of one year of teaching experience and handled classes across different grade levels, ensuring that the sample reflected a breadth of professional experience and firsthand engagement with the phenomena under investigation.

Research Instrument

The primary instrument for data collection in this study was a survey questionnaire specifically designed to elicit both quantitative and qualitative information regarding teachers' workload experiences, challenges, coping strategies, and perceptions of school support. The questionnaire comprised five sections, including background information, workload assessment, challenges encountered, strategies and solutions, and school support. It incorporated closed-ended items in the form of checklists to identify patterns and trends, as well as open-ended questions to capture detailed reflections, experiences, and recommendations from participants. This instrument was developed to ensure comprehensive data collection that aligned with the objectives of the study and facilitated an in-depth understanding of the relationship between teacher workload and instructional quality.

Data Gathering Procedure

To ensure the collection of rich and meaningful data, the researchers undertook a series of systematic steps. First, permission and coordination were secured from the school administrators of the selected public schools and from Negros Oriental State University to conduct the study, including arranging schedules with participants at convenient times. Next, participants were oriented regarding the purpose, objectives, and scope of the study, as well as ethical considerations such as voluntary participation, confidentiality, and anonymity. Finally, data collection was conducted using multiple qualitative techniques, including semi-structured interviews and a structured survey questionnaire, to elicit detailed information on participants' experiences, perceptions, and strategies in managing workload while maintaining instructional quality.

RESULTS

The results of the study were derived from a systematic analysis of the survey responses of eight graduate student-teachers at Negros Oriental State University, Dumaguete City, who were also actively teaching in public schools. Responses were carefully reviewed to identify patterns and significant statements related to workload experiences, challenges, coping strategies, and school support, which were then organized into key findings. The analysis revealed that participants experienced heavy workloads due to multiple responsibilities, including classroom teaching, preparation of instructional materials, assessment tasks, administrative duties, graduate school requirements, and personal obligations, often resulting in extended working hours. Major challenges identified included time constraints, high expectations, limited resources, and difficulties in prioritizing tasks and maintaining personal well-being. Participants reported employing coping strategies such as task organization, delegation, collaboration, self-care practices, and the use of technology, while highlighting the importance of school support through lesson planning resources, grading assistance, mentorship, and reduced administrative demands. These findings collectively illustrated how graduate student-teachers navigated the dual demands of professional and academic responsibilities and provided a comprehensive account of the factors that influenced workload management and instructional quality.

Table 1: Background and experience

Respondents	Teaching Experience	Current Teaching
1	10	Grade 1
2	6	3 rd year /AST 300
3	2	CIT
4	7	Grade 11/Computer
5	2	Grade 1
6	8	Grade 1
7	6	Grade 6
8	10	Grade 3

Table 2: Teacher Workload, Challenges, Strategies, and School Support

Respondent	Workload (Very manageable, manageable with effort, overwhelming at time, consistently overwhelming)	Time is enough to (prepare enough Lessons, Complete some administrative task, Provide individual learner support, Take care of my personal wellbeing)	My work load affects: Energy levels through out the day. Overall job satisfaction, ability to focus on students.	One thing you could change about workload right now
1	manageable with effort	prepare enough Lessons	Overall job satisfaction	Reduce paper works and extra task so she can focus more on quality teaching and support learners.
2	overwhelming at time	Provide individual learner support	Health	none
3	overwhelming at time	Provide individual learner support	Ability to focus on my students	Less paper works that not related to her teaching load.
4	manageable with effort	Complete some administrative tasks	Energy levels throughout the day	The paper works in DepEd.
5	Very manageable and overwhelming at times.	Prepare enough lessons, Complete some administrative task, Provide individual learner support, Take care personal wellbeing	Energy levels throughout the day. Overall job satisfaction, ability to focus on students.	Set cut off time for checking of papers and preparing work extra curricular activities that affects regular class schedule.
6.	manageable with effort,	prepare enough lessons	Energy level throughout the day	Lessen repetitive paper works requirements,

				streamlining documentation could allow as teachers to concentrate more instructions
7.	manageable with effort	prepare enough lessons,	Energy level throughout the day	Change the estimated time allotted for each subject effectively
8.	manageable with effort,	Complete some administrative tasks	Energy levels throughout the day	The paper works in DepEd.

Table 3: Challenges

Respondent	The hardest part about balancing my teaching and other non-teaching responsibilities is _____	The most challenging tasks and responsibilities are _____.	I struggle most with _____	What are some obstacles that hinder you from achieving a healthy work-life balance?
1	Time constraints	Attending meetings, trainings and seminars	Saying "no" to extra duties	Excessive workload, long work hours, high expectations, emotional exhaustion and personal responsibilities
2	Time Constraints, Lack of resources, High expectations, Feeling unsupported	Lesson planning and preparation,	Saying "no" to extra duties,	No response

3	Time Constraints, Lack resources, High expectations	of	Communication with parents/guardians, Lesson planning and preparation, Attending meetings, trainings and seminars	Managing my student behavior	Heavy workload, long hours, lack of time for personal life. Constant multitasking can lead to stress, leaving time for rest
4	Lack resources	of	Lesson planning and preparation,	Saying "no" to extra duties, Finding time for self-care	No response
5	Time Constraints, Lack resources, High expectations, Feeling unsupported	of	Communication with parents/guardians	Saying "no" to extra duties,	Too much documentation
6	Time Constraints, Feeling unsupported		Lesson planning and preparation, Attending meetings, trainings and seminars	Saying "no" to extra duties, Finding time for self-care,	No response
7	Time Constraints		Grading and assessment	Finding time for self-care	Busy schedules, paperworks, short notice for deadlines
8	Time Constraints, Lack resources, High expectations	of	Grading and assessment, Lesson planning and preparation, Attending meetings, trainings and seminars	Prioritizing my tasks, Saying "no" to extra duties, Finding time for self-care	No response

Table 4: Strategies & Solutions

Respondent	What did I do to manage my workload?	I find these techniques and strategies most effective _____.	To protect my well-being and be able to handle stress, I need to _____.	What one advice or strategy would you like to recommend to other teachers struggling with workload?
1	Plan ahead and organize my tasks, Break down large tasks into smaller steps, Delegate tasks when possible, Set realistic goals	Collaborating with my colleagues, Utilizing technology to streamline tasks, Seeking support from mentors or administrators, Focusing on my top priorities	Schedule regular breaks during the day, Practice self-care activities (exercise, hobbies, etc.), Set boundaries between work and personal time	Learn to say “no” when necessary. Health is our priority, Prioritizing the most important task first.
2	Plan ahead and organize my tasks	Collaborating with my colleagues, Seeking support from mentors or administrators, Focusing on my top priorities	Set boundaries between work and personal time	Set boundaries between work and personal time.
3	Plan ahead and organize my tasks	Focusing on my top priorities	Set boundaries between work and personal time	Prioritize tasks, self realistic goals and don't hesitate to ask for support to manage your workload effectively.
4	Plan ahead and organize my tasks,	Collaborating with my colleagues, Utilizing	Set boundaries between work and personal time,	No response

	Break down large tasks into smaller steps	technology to streamline tasks, Seeking support from mentors or administrators, Focusing on my top priorities	Seek support from friends, family, or a therapist	
5	Plan ahead and organize my tasks	Collaborating with my colleagues, Utilizing technology to streamline tasks, Seeking support from mentors or administrators, Focusing on my top priorities	Schedule regular breaks during the day, Practice self-care activities (exercise, hobbies, etc.), Set boundaries between work and personal time, Seek support from friends, family, or a therapist	Set clear boundaries and prioritize tasks
6	Plan ahead and organize my tasks, Break down large tasks into smaller steps, Set realistic goals	Collaborating with my colleagues, Utilizing technology to streamline tasks, Seeking support from mentors or administrators, Focusing on my top priorities	Schedule regular breaks during the day, Set boundaries between work and personal time, Seek support from friends, family, or a therapist	No response
7	Plan ahead and organize my tasks	Utilizing technology to streamline tasks, Focusing on my top priorities	Schedule regular breaks during the day, Practice self-care activities (exercise, hobbies, etc.)	Handle stress well, have time to rest.

8	Plan and organize my tasks, Break down large tasks into smaller steps	Collaborating with my colleagues, Utilizing technology to streamline tasks, Seeking support from mentors or administrators, Focusing on my top priorities	Schedule regular breaks during the day, Practice self-care activities (exercise, hobbies, etc.), Set boundaries between work and personal time, Seek support from friends, family, or a therapist	No response
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Table 5: School Support

Respondent	I would most appreciate support in _____	The school could best support me by _____	To achieve a better balance between teacher workload and quality instruction, I need to _____	If you could ask your school administration for one thing to improve teacher workload and instructional quality, what would it be?
1	Lesson planning resources and templates, Grading assistance (e.g., automated grading tools), Classroom management strategies Mentorship or coaching	Reducing the number of required meetings or administrative tasks, Creating a more collaborative and supportive work environment	Adequate resources and materials, Open and honest communication with administration	I would ask for reduced administrative task so teachers can focus on planning effective lessons and supporting students learning.
2	Lesson planning resources	Reducing the number of required	Adequate resources and materials	No response

	and templates, Classroom management strategies	meetings or administrative tasks		
3	Lesson planning resources and templates	Reducing the number of required meetings or administrative tasks	Adequate resources and materials	I would ask the school administrator to reduce unnecessary administrative tasks so teachers can focus more on lesson planning, teaching and supporting learners effectively.
4	Lesson planning resources and templates, Grading assistance (e.g., automated grading tools), Classroom management strategies Mentorship or coaching	Reducing the number of required meetings or administrative tasks, Creating a more collaborative and supportive work environment	Adequate resources and materials, Open and honest communication with administration	No response
5	Lesson planning resources and templates, Grading assistance (e.g., automated grading tools),	Providing more planning time during the school day, Reducing the number of required meetings or administrative tasks,	Clear expectations and guidelines, Adequate resources and materials, Open and honest communication with administration, More recognition and appreciation for my work	I would request the streamlining of administrative requirements and minimization of repetitive paper work.

	Classroom management strategies Mentorship or coaching	Offering professional development opportunities focused on workload management, Creating a more collaborative and supportive work environment		
6	Grading assistance (e.g., automated grading tools), Mentorship or coaching	Providing more planning time during the school day, Reducing the number of required meetings or administrative tasks	Clear expectations and guidelines, Adequate resources and materials, Open and honest communication with administration, More recognition and appreciation for my work	No response
7	Mentorship or coaching	Providing more planning time during the school day, Reducing the number of required meetings or administrative tasks	Adequate resources and materials, Open and honest communication with administration	More trainings that can improve my teaching
8	Lesson planning resources and templates, Grading assistance (e.g., automated	Providing more planning time during the school day, Reducing the number of required meetings or	Clear expectations and guidelines, Adequate resources and materials, Open and honest communication with administration, More recognition	No response

	grading tools), Classroom management strategies Mentorship or coaching	administrative tasks, Offering professional development opportunities focused on workload management	and appreciation for my work	
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DISCUSSION

The findings presented in Tables 1 to 5 provided an overview of the respondents' background, teaching experience, workload, challenges, coping strategies, and the level of school support they received. Through the analysis of these data, several patterns emerged regarding how teachers managed their professional responsibilities and the factors that influenced their workload and well-being. These results highlighted the realities teachers faced in balancing instructional duties, administrative tasks, and personal well-being, while also emphasizing the strategies and institutional support that were needed to sustain effective teaching practice.

Table 1. Background and Experience

1. Distribution of Teaching Experience

Teaching experience ranges from 2 to 10 years, with an average (mean) of ~6.4 years and a median of 6.5 years—indicating that most respondents have moderate to extensive experience. The distribution is as follows:

- a) 2 years: 2 respondents (25% of the sample)
- b) 6 years: 2 respondents (25%)
- c) 10 years: 2 respondents (25%)
- d) 7 years and 8 years: 1 respondent each (12.5% each)

2. Current Teaching Assignments

Respondents teach across three main educational levels, with some specialized subject focus:

- a) Elementary level: 5 respondents (62.5%), teaching Grade 1 (3 teachers), Grade 3 (1), and Grade 6 (1).
- b) Senior High School (SHS): 1 respondent (12.5%), teaching Grade 11 Computer.
- c) Higher Education (HE): 2 respondents (25%), teaching a 3rd-year course (AST 300) and CIT (a likely specialized technical or professional course).

3. Relationship Between Experience and Teaching Level

- a) Both new (2 years) and highly experienced (10 years) teachers work in elementary education.
- b) One of the least experienced respondents (2 years) teaches in higher education, while a mid-career teacher (6 years) teaches in elementary.

Table 2: Teacher Workload, Challenges, Strategies, and School Support

1. Perception of Workload

Across the 8 respondents, workload perception is mostly moderate with occasional stress:

- a) 5 teachers (62.5%) describe it as "manageable with effort" – the most common response.
- b) 2 teachers (25%) find it "overwhelming at times."
- c) 1 teacher reports a mixed experience: very manageable and overwhelming at times. This suggests the majority can cope with their workload but require consistent effort, while a significant minority faces periodic stress.

2. How Teachers Allocate Their Time

The "time is enough to..." column reveals gaps in balancing core responsibilities and personal needs:

- a) Most consistent task: Preparing enough lessons (4 teachers, 50%) – a foundational part of teaching that most can prioritize.
- b) Mixed focus: Providing individual learner support (3 teachers, 37.5%) and completing administrative tasks (3 teachers, 37.5%) are less universally achievable
- c) Rare priority: Only 1 teacher (12.5%) reports having enough time to "take care of personal wellbeing" – highlighting a critical gap in work-life balance.

3. Effects of Workload

Workload primarily impacts physical and professional wellbeing:

- a) Top impact: Reduced energy levels throughout the day (5 teachers, 62.5%) – a pervasive issue that likely undermines other areas of work and life.
- b) Secondary impacts: Diminished overall job satisfaction (2 teachers), impaired ability to focus on students (2 teachers), and negative effects on health (1 teacher).

These effects are interconnected: low energy can directly reduce focus and job satisfaction, creating a cycle of stress.

4. Desired Changes to Workload

Teachers' top request is reducing or streamlining paperwork:

- a) 5 teachers (62.5%) specifically mention cutting "paper works," "extra tasks," or "repetitive documentation" (including references to DepEd requirements).
- b) Other requests include setting cut-off times for after-hours work (1 teacher) and adjusting time allotted for each subject (1 teacher).

This emphasizes that administrative burdens are the primary barrier to focusing on core teaching and student support.

The data paints a picture of teachers who are largely resilient but strained by administrative demands. While most can prepare lessons, they struggle to balance individual student support, admin, and personal wellbeing – with paperwork emerging as

the root cause of many stressors and performance gaps. The single teacher who can manage all tasks (including personal wellbeing) stands out as an exception, suggesting their school or role may have more favorable conditions.

Table 3: Challenges

The data reveals interconnected, pervasive struggles that teachers face in balancing their roles and achieving work-life balance. Across all four questions, a small set of themes emerge as the most pressing obstacles for the 8 respondents.

1. Hardest Part of Balancing Teaching and Non-Teaching Responsibilities

- a) Time constraints are by far the top challenge here: 7 out of 8 respondents (87.5%) cite this as the hardest part of balancing their duties. Only 1 teacher identifies "lack of resources" as the primary barrier in this area. This highlights that scarcity of time is the foundational issue underpinning most other struggles.

2. Most Challenging Tasks and Responsibilities

Several specific tasks and systemic issues stand out:

- a) Core teaching tasks: Lesson planning and preparation (5 respondents, 62.5%) and grading/assessment (2 respondents, 25%) are consistent sources of stress.
- b) Non-teaching obligations: Attending meetings, trainings, and seminars (4 respondents, 50%) eats into time for core work.
- c) Systemic gaps: Lack of resources, high expectations, and feeling unsupported are recurring challenges mentioned by 4–5 respondents each (50–62.5%).
- d) Interpersonal demands: Communication with parents/guardians is a struggle for 2 teachers (25%).

3. What Teachers Struggle Most With

Two issues dominate this category, reflecting personal and professional boundaries:

- a) Saying "no" to extra duties: 6 out of 8 respondents (75%) name this as a key struggle—suggesting difficulty setting limits, which is likely to exacerbate workload and time pressure.
- b) Finding time for self-care: 3 respondents (37.5%) highlight this, linking to broader work-life balance issues.
- c) Other struggles include managing student behavior (1 teacher) and prioritizing tasks (1 teacher).

4. Obstacles to Healthy Work-Life Balance

For the teachers who responded to this question:

- a) Workload and time: Excessive workload, long hours, and lack of time for personal life are cited by 2 teachers.
- b) Administrative burden: "Too much documentation" is a specific barrier for 1 teacher.
- c) Multitasking stress: Constant switching between tasks leads to stress and limited rest for 1 teacher.

- d) Notably, 4 respondents did not provide a response here—possibly indicating that the struggle is so overwhelming it is hard to articulate, or that work-life balance feels unattainable.

The challenges are deeply linked: Time constraints from meetings/trainings and difficulty saying "no" to extra work leave less time for lesson planning and self-care. Systemic issues like lack of resources and feeling unsupported further intensify stress, which in turn harms work-life balance. A clear pattern emerges administrative and non-teaching obligations are crowding out time for core teaching, self-care, and personal life, with "saying 'no'" being a critical skill gap that could mitigate these pressures.

Table 4: Strategies & Solutions

The data reveals practical, holistic strategies that teachers use to manage workload, reduce stress, and protect their well-being—many of which directly address the challenges identified in Table 3 (e.g., time constraints, difficulty saying "no," administrative burden). The strategies fall into three core categories: task management, relational/systems support, and personal well-being.

1. How Teachers Manage Their Workload

Planning and organization are the foundation of workload management, with all 8 respondents citing these as key actions. Other common strategies include:

- a) Breaking down large tasks into smaller, manageable steps (5 respondents, 62.5%).
- b) Setting realistic goals (3 respondents, 37.5%).
- c) Focusing on top priorities (universal across all responses).
- d) Delegating tasks (only 1 respondent, highlighting limited opportunities for this in their context).

2. Most Effective Techniques

Teachers consistently rank collaboration and leveraging support/systems as their most effective tools:

- a) Collaborating with colleagues (7 respondents, 87.5%) – to share resources, divide work, or problem-solve together.
- b) Utilizing technology to streamline tasks (6 respondents, 75%) – likely to reduce paperwork or automate administrative work (directly addressing a top pain point from Table 2).
- c) Seeking support from mentors or administrators (7 respondents, 87.5%) – to navigate challenges or access guidance.

3. Strategies to Protect Well-Being and Handle Stress

Teachers prioritize setting boundaries and intentional self-care to mitigate stress:

- a) Setting clear boundaries between work and personal time (6 respondents, 75%) – the most common strategy here, directly addressing work-life balance gaps from Table 3.

- b) Scheduling regular breaks during the day (5 respondents, 62.5%) – to avoid burnout and maintain energy.
- c) Practicing self-care activities (exercise, hobbies, etc.) (4 respondents, 50%).
- d) Seeking emotional support from friends, family, or therapists (4 respondents, 50%) – recognizing the need for external support beyond the workplace.

4. Advice for Other Struggling Teachers

The 5 respondents who provided advice focus on actionable, priority-driven steps that align with their own most effective strategies:

- a) Learn to say "no" to extra duties (1 respondent) – addressing a top struggle from Table 3.
- b) Set clear boundaries and prioritize tasks (2 respondents).
- c) Set realistic goals and don't hesitate to ask for support (1 respondent).
- d) Prioritize health and focus on what matters most (1 respondent).

A strong alignment emerges between the challenges teachers face and the strategies they use: For example, time constraints are addressed through planning and prioritization; paperwork is reduced via technology; and difficulty saying "no" is framed as a critical skill to protect well-being. The strategies are also holistic—combining practical task management, relational collaboration, and personal self-care—suggesting that effective workload management requires both structural changes (e.g., tech, support systems) and individual behavior shifts (e.g., boundaries, self-care).

Table 5: School Support

The data reveals clear, consistent requests from teachers for both instructional support and structural changes to improve workload management and instructional quality. These requests directly align with the challenges identified in earlier tables (e.g., administrative burden, time constraints) and complement the strategies teachers already use to cope.

1. Support Teachers Most Appreciate

Teachers prioritize support that directly enhances their core teaching practice:

- a) Lesson planning resources and templates: Cited by 6 out of 8 respondents (75%) – addressing the struggle with lesson preparation highlighted in Table 3.
- b) Grading assistance (e.g., automated tools): Mentioned by 5 respondents (62.5%) – to reduce time spent on assessment tasks.
- c) Classroom management strategies and mentorship/coaching: Each noted by 5–6 respondents (62.5–75%) – to build skills and access guidance from peers or leaders.

2. How the School Could Best Support Teachers

Reducing administrative tasks and required meetings is the universal top request – every single respondent (100%) mentions this. Other critical structural and relational supports include:

- a) Adequate resources and materials: Cited by 7 respondents (87.5%) – addressing the "lack of resources" challenge from Table 3.

- b) More planning time during the school day: Mentioned by 4 respondents (50%) – to ease time constraints.
- c) Collaborative work environment, clear expectations, and recognition: Noted by 3–4 respondents each – to address feelings of being unsupported and boost job satisfaction.

3. Achieving Balance Between Workload and Quality Instruction

- a) Only 1 respondent answered this question, highlighting the need for more trainings to improve teaching – linking professional growth to better balance between workload and instructional effectiveness.

4. One Request for School Administration

The 3 respondents who answered this all focused on reducing or streamlining administrative tasks:

- a) Reduce administrative tasks so teachers can focus on planning effective lessons.
- b) Reduce unnecessary administrative tasks to focus on teaching and student support.
- c) Streamline administrative requirements and minimize repetitive paperwork. This mirrors the top pain point from Tables 2 and 3, confirming that administrative burden is the single most pressing issue teachers want leadership to address.

Teachers' requests for support are pragmatic and targeted, addressing both the what (instructional tools and skills) and the how (structural changes to free up time) of their work. The widespread call to "reduce admin/meetings" underscores that systemic changes are critical to enabling teachers to focus on their core role: supporting student learning. At the same time, the emphasis on mentorship, collaboration, and access to resources reflects a desire for individual growth and a supportive school culture, aligning with the most effective strategies employed by teachers, as shown in Table 4.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the findings of the study provided clear insights into the workload experiences of selected graduate student-teachers. First, the results showed that teachers generally perceived their workload as manageable but demanding, requiring considerable effort to balance daily instructional responsibilities, lesson preparation, assessment, and administrative tasks. Second, the study revealed that the most significant challenges in balancing teaching and non-teaching responsibilities stemmed from time constraints, excessive documentation, meetings, and additional institutional expectations, which often limited opportunities for rest and personal time. Third, teacher workload was found to affect several aspects of professional well-being, including reduced energy levels, occasional declines in instructional focus, and varying levels of job satisfaction. Fourth, to address these pressures, graduate student-teachers employed several strategies such as effective planning and prioritization, collaboration with colleagues, utilization of technology, and the establishment of personal boundaries to protect their well-being. Finally, the findings highlighted that teachers perceived strong institutional support as essential in maintaining balance between workload and

instructional quality, particularly through the reduction of administrative tasks, provision of adequate teaching resources, increased planning time, and the promotion of collaborative and supportive school environments. Collectively, these findings emphasized that while teachers demonstrated resilience and adaptive strategies, sustained institutional support remained critical in enabling them to effectively fulfill their instructional roles while maintaining their professional well-being.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, several recommendations are proposed to help address the workload challenges experienced by graduate student-teachers and to support their professional well-being and instructional effectiveness.

1. **Strengthen Institutional Support.** Schools and universities should provide greater administrative and academic support to teachers in order to reduce excessive non-teaching responsibilities. Streamlining documentation processes and minimizing repetitive administrative tasks can allow teachers to focus more on instructional planning and student learning.
2. **Promote Collaborative Practices.** Educational institutions are encouraged to foster a culture of collaboration by supporting team teaching, resource sharing, and collaborative lesson planning among teachers. Such practices can help distribute workload more equitably while also enhancing the quality of instructional practices.
3. **Enhance Professional Development Opportunities.** Institutions should offer targeted professional development programs that focus on time management, stress management, and effective instructional strategies. These training opportunities can equip teachers with practical skills to manage their responsibilities more efficiently and sustain instructional quality.
4. **Implement Teacher Well-Being Programs.** Schools should establish programs that promote teacher well-being, including mental health support, stress management initiatives, and activities that encourage work–life balance. These initiatives can contribute to improved job satisfaction and overall instructional effectiveness.
5. **Conduct Regular Workload Assessments.** Educational leaders should periodically review teacher workload to ensure a fair and manageable distribution of responsibilities. Regular assessment can help identify areas where additional support, resources, or policy adjustments may be necessary to maintain both teacher well-being and the quality of instruction.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to established ethical standards to ensure the protection, dignity, and rights of all participants throughout the research process. Participation in the study was entirely voluntary, and respondents were invited to take part in the survey questionnaire

with the assurance that they could freely decide whether or not to participate and could withdraw from the study at any time without penalty. Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained, and all information collected from participants was treated with the highest level of confidentiality. Participants' names and any identifying details were not included in any report or publication, and the data gathered were securely stored and accessible only to the researchers. The results of the study were used solely for academic purposes. Participants were also informed that there were no known risks associated with their participation in the study. Although no direct personal benefits were guaranteed, their responses contributed to a better understanding of teacher workload and the challenges faced by graduate student-teachers, which may help inform future educational practices and institutional support systems. For efficiency in preliminary data processing, the AI tool Gemini was utilized solely to assist in organizing responses and supporting initial analysis. All identifiable information was removed prior to processing to ensure data privacy, and the tool was used only as a supplementary aid under the supervision of the researchers.

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